

THE ESSENCE OF CONFERENCE TOURISM, ANALYSIS OF THE STATE AND PROSPECTS OF ITS DEVELOPMENT IN AZERBAIJAN

Hasanov A.

Doctor of Economics, Professor, Ganja State University, Ganja, Azerbaijan

ORCID: 0000-0001-8044-2711

Valiyev G.

Master's student, Ganja State University, Ganja, Azerbaijan

ABSTRACT

This study examined the development of conference tourism in Azerbaijan and its impact on the country's economy. Conference tourism diversifies the economy and tourism sector of the country, creates new jobs and strengthens international relations by organizing international events and attracting participants to the country. It is noted that in order to accelerate the development of this type of tourism, it is necessary to continuously improve infrastructure, expand cooperation with various regional and international organizations, and monitor international experience.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, conference tourism, international organizations, multifunctional halls.

Introduction. Azerbaijan's tourism sector is developing rapidly. Various government measures and successful tourism strategies are being implemented for the dynamic development of the national tourism industry, including various types and forms of tourism. In this regard, certain types of tourism are developing, one of which is conference tourism. At the same time, it should be noted that the potential of conference tourism in the country has not yet been fully utilized in the tourist cycle. The organization of international events and conferences is important for economic diversification, balanced regional development and recognition of the organizational and economic potential of Azerbaijan in the field of conference tourism development in the global market. The development of conference tourism can also have a significant impact on the economic and cultural life of the country. Thus, the development of conference tourism will both strengthen the global political, economic and cultural integration of Azerbaijan, and increase additional foreign exchange earnings, since conference tourism is one of the most profitable types of tourism.

The object of the research is the conference tourism system in Azerbaijan, including its development within the framework of the country's tourism sector, infrastructure and international integration.

The subject of the research is the organizational and economic issues that arise in the process of organizing and developing conference tourism in Azerbaijan.

The purpose of the study. To conduct research and present scientifically and theoretically sound proposals for the development of conference tourism in Azerbaijan.

Scientific novelty of the research. As a result of the study, it was found that Azerbaijan has favorable conditions and the necessary potential, which creates the basis for the development of conference tourism. However, this potential has not yet been fully exploited. For the development of this type of tourism, it is necessary to take additional measures to create a new infrastructure for the effective use of opportunities and potential, improve the skills of conference tourism organizers, expand international cooperation and exchange

experience. Theoretically and empirically sound proposals have been put forward to address these issues.

The information base of the study is formed by data and reports from the State Tourism Agency of Azerbaijan, the State Statistical Committee and various institutions, information about organized and planned international organizations, conferences and events, and research materials on the relevant topic.

Methodology and research methods. The methodological basis of the research is a systematic approach to the problem. The research used methods of analysis, comparison, generalization, statistical analysis, synthesis and deduction.

Discussion. Tourism, as in many countries, is one of the types of economic activity that plays an important role in the socio-economic development of Azerbaijan and provides a substantial impetus to the overall development of the national economic system [2]. Taking this factor into account, in the "Azerbaijan 2030: National Priorities of socio-economic Development" adopted in 2021, the tourism sector is among the eight important and priority areas of strategic economic development of Azerbaijan [1]. The natural tourist resources available in the country, the social and special tourist infrastructure, which has been constantly updated and improved in recent years in accordance with modern requirements, as well as other favorable conditions create favorable conditions for the diversified development of national tourism [3]. In particular, the growth of economic potential against the background of the overall development of Azerbaijan has raised financial support to a high level, which is one of the important factors of development, and has further expanded the real opportunities for the integrated development of tourism.

Currently, a number of types of tourism are developing and gaining popularity in the system of tourist services. One of these types is conference tourism. The opportunities for the development of this type of tourism in Azerbaijan are considerably broad. Conference tourism is a type of tourism that occurs for the purpose of people traveling to other countries in connection with international conferences, seminars, exhibitions and other events. Conference tourism is also important

as an important type of tourism that strengthens the economy, culture and international relations of the country, and its development gives a powerful impetus to the overall development of the national tourism industry.

The accelerated development of the national economy in recent years has allowed Azerbaijan to strengthen its influence and ranking in the world, strengthen its economic potential and penetrate the sphere of interests of many political, economic and cultural centers. This necessitated the regular organization of international events of various levels and orientations in Azerbaijan, including conferences on various topics and events. Increasing the intensity of organizing such events provides a substantial impetus to the development of conference tourism in Azerbaijan, as conference tourism is considered and developed as one of the means of organizing various local, regional and international events and meetings.

Such events attract tourists to the country, contributing to the development of both the economy and the strengthening of international relations. Azerbaijan has repeatedly organized events of the “Organization of Turkic States” (OTS), the “Organization of Islamic Cooperation” (OIC), and the “Commonwealth of Independent States” (CIS), as well as successfully hosted international events and conferences dedicated to solving global environmental problems and other topics, such as COP 29. These events provide Azerbaijan with new opportunities to gain international recognition, expand new channels of cooperation, strengthen the economy and create conditions for the accumulation of certain experience. In addition, such events contribute to the creation and continuous improvement of high-level infrastructure, give an impetus to improving the quality of tourist services, as well as the production and supply of new types of services.

In general, Azerbaijan has broad opportunities, natural, economic and infrastructural potential for the organization and development of various types of tourism and pursues a targeted policy for the rational use of this potential [4].

The results of the discussion. The development of conference tourism in Azerbaijan has been growing rapidly in recent years due to various factors. There are several key factors in the development of conference tourism in Azerbaijan. First of all, Azerbaijan's geographical location and strategic importance make the country an ideal venue for international events. In addition, Baku, Ganja, Gabala and other cities, being hubs for international flights, provide convenient conditions for guests to travel to the conference.

Baku is the most important center of Azerbaijan both economically and in terms of tourism. The well-developed infrastructure, modern conference centers and hotels in Baku create a very favorable and suitable environment for world-class events. At the same time, Azerbaijan's successful integration into global processes, the developing common infrastructure and the serious transformation and development of the tourism sector have created additional incentives for holding international events. International events and conferences held in Azerbaijan also play an important role in the international recognition of the country and the expansion of its relations.

In addition, by providing a commendable example and experience in organizing and holding international events at a high level, Azerbaijan creates incentives for participation in international events in countries around the world and organizations at various levels. This also creates a serious demand for the organization of conferences on various topics in the country. Consequently, the number of conferences held in Azerbaijan in this field has been steadily increasing in recent years. The dynamics of this growth is reflected in the figure 1.

Figure 1. The dynamics of events at various levels held in Azerbaijan in 2018-2024. *Built by the authors on the basis of statistical data from the State Tourism Agency [10].

As can be seen from graph 1, there has been an increase in the number of conferences and other similar events organized since 2018. In 2019, the introduction

of restrictions related to the risks caused by the COVID-19 pandemic led to a serious reduction in the

organization of international events, and only 60 international events on various topics were held in the country. Starting in 2020, the number of international events is increasing annually, reaching 210 in 2024. The growing number of conferences devoted to international and regional issues is an indicator of the development of conference tourism in Azerbaijan. Thus, the policy pursued in the field of organization and development of conference tourism continues successfully and considerable promise.

It should be noted that Azerbaijan regularly hosts summits of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS), conferences of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), various events of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) and other conferences on international issues. The largest international conference on global climate change, COP 29, was also held in Baku in 2024.

The Organization of Turkic States is an international organization established with the aim of developing political, economic and cultural cooperation between the Turkic-speaking states. The foundation for the establishment of the organization was laid by the Nakhchivan Agreement, signed by the Turkic-speaking states on October 3, 2009 in Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan. The original name is the Cooperation Council of Turkic-speaking States (Turkic Council). Later, at the Istanbul summit in 2021, the organization's name was officially changed to the Organization of Turkic States [5; 9].

Regular conferences of the Organization of Turkic States are organized, in which Azerbaijan actively participates. The organization's international conference, held in Baku in 2023, was attended by government agencies, heads of the Organization of Turkic States, heads of historical cities and reserves of Turkic states, experts and representatives of international organizations with which the Organization cooperates, as well as representatives of the press. The Baku Declaration on the Protection of Turkic Monuments of the Organization's member states was signed at the international conference. The main goal of the declaration is to expand cooperation in the field of joint assistance to the protection, restoration and popularization of cultural heritage among historical cities and reserves of the member and observer countries of the Organization of Turkic States. Within the framework of the conference, experts from historical cities and reserves of the Organization of Turkic States member countries and representatives of international organizations visited the fortress cities of Icherisheher, Shusha and Shaki and got acquainted with historical monuments, as well as restoration work carried out in the post-war period.

The Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) is an international organization created to strengthen cooperation between Muslim countries. The OIC was founded in 1969 at a summit held in Rabat, Morocco. The main reason for the creation of the organization was the arson of the Al-Aqsa Mosque in 1969. This incident showed the importance of uniting Muslim countries and developing a common position. The main goals of the organization are to develop political, economic and cultural cooperation between the member

states, strengthen Islamic solidarity and protect the interests of Muslim peoples, promote international peace and security, support the position of Muslim countries on the Palestinian issue and promote cooperation in the field of education, science and technology [8].

Today, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) is one of the largest international organizations in the world. The Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) Conferences are one of the most important international events bringing together 57 member countries from all over the world. Economic, political, social and cultural issues are discussed at these events. Azerbaijan's close cooperation with the OIC and the holding of such conferences in the country demonstrate that Azerbaijan plays an important role in solving socio-economic, cultural, environmental and other problems of the Islamic world and in the overall integration process.

The Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) was established on December 8, 1991 in Belovezhskaya Pushcha in Belarus on the basis of the Belovezhskaya Agreements signed by the leaders of Russia, Ukraine and Belarus. This agreement actually formalized the collapse of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics. Later, at a meeting held in Almaty on December 21, 1991, other former Soviet republics joined the CIS, and the organization's activities expanded. The CIS was established in 1991 after the collapse of the USSR to maintain political, economic and humanitarian ties between the newly independent states [6; 7].

The Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) Conferences are a platform for discussing political, economic, security and other issues of countries located in the post-Soviet space. Azerbaijan is an active member of the CIS, and the activities of this organization are aimed at ensuring the stability and development of the region. To date, Azerbaijan has hosted a number of CIS conferences. Examples include the "Conference on Management of Science and Technology", "Conference on Oil Refining and Petrochemistry", "Conferences of banking organizations of the CIS countries", etc. Such conferences play an important role in the country's international relations and strengthen Azerbaijan's position as an influential force in the region.

One of the international events organized at a high level and successfully completed in Baku was the "Conference of the Parties" (COP), where issues of combating global climate change were discussed. The "Partners Conference", which joined the Convention, aims to solve quite significant problems. The COP, whose secretariat is located in Bonn, is the highest decision-making body of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. Every year, representatives of governments from all over the world gather at COP to call for joint efforts to prevent and eliminate the effects of climate change.

Azerbaijan hosted COP-29 in 2024. The 11-day conference focused on the experiences and traditions formed by COP-29 in the field of sustainable development and combating climate change at the local and global levels. The conference was attended by delegations from 198 countries that signed the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change.

Azerbaijan's successful organization of international events, along with an increase in the country's tourism revenues, creates conditions for the development of business ties with local economic entities. These events also put Azerbaijan in the spotlight as one of the successful organizers of international events in the region and in the world.

Conference tourism has a significant impact not only on the development of tourism, but also on the local economy. The conference participants consumption of accommodation, food, and transportation services, as well as the purchase of local products, revitalize the local economy, provide employment, and increase the flow of foreign currency into the country. Assessing the impact of conference tourism on the country's economy, we argue that the development of this type of tourism leads to the development of local businesses and the creation of new jobs.

In addition, the development of conference tourism accelerates the development of other service sectors. The development of conference tourism contributes to the development of the country's tourism infrastructure and stimulates activities related to the construction and use of new facilities in the tourism industry, multifunctional conference halls. This process has a positive impact not only on the tourism sector, but also on the development of sectors directly and indirectly related to the hospitality industry.

There are also some difficulties preventing the faster development of conference tourism in Azerbaijan. Strengthening cooperation with international organizations and other experienced organizers of conference tourism will help overcome difficulties in this area, solve problems, raise organizational issues to a higher level and accelerate the more successful development of this type of tourism. At the same time, it is very important to train experienced and professional conference organizers and train specialists in this field. Studying international experience and adapting this experience to local conditions is essential for the effective development of conference tourism.

The increased interest in the development of conference tourism in Azerbaijan in recent years further enhances the potential of national tourism. The favorable strategic and geographical location of the country, the development of modern infrastructure and the expansion of international relations create additional prospects for Azerbaijan in hosting international conferences and events. The development of this type of tourism will contribute to both the diversification of the tourism sector and the development of other sectors of the economy.

Holding international conferences on various issues in Azerbaijan, including events such as COP 29, enhances the country's international prestige and creates an opportunity to establish mutually beneficial high-level relations with most countries of the world. Such events have a positive impact not only on the development of tourism, but also on the local economy, creating new jobs and stimulating the development of the local tourism services sector.

However, there are some difficulties in the development of conference tourism in Azerbaijan. In order

to overcome these difficulties and disadvantages and effectively develop conference tourism, it is important to strengthen international cooperation in this field, enhance the experience of local specialists and constantly improve the special infrastructure of conference tourism.

In addition, increased cooperation between the public and private sectors is essential to ensure the sustainable and successful development of conference tourism. Government support in this area will ensure the attraction of international events to the country and the growth of conference tourism as a new economic opportunity for Azerbaijan. In general, the development of conference tourism in Azerbaijan will strengthen international relations and turn the country into an important tourist center in the region and around the world.

Conclusion. Conference tourism is one of the most promising and profitable types of tourism in the development of the national tourism industry. Azerbaijan has a huge potential for the organization and development of this type of tourism. Systematic measures are being implemented and conferences of various levels are being organized to make effective use of this potential. At the same time, in order to ensure the sustainable development of conference tourism in the country, it is advisable to implement the following proposals put forward by us:

- it is necessary to develop the infrastructure and create new multifunctional conference halls. The availability of high-class conference centers offering comprehensive services, modern accommodation facilities and a network of transportation services will create additional incentives for development in this area.;

- expand cooperation with international organizations. The further development of Azerbaijan's relations with international organizations will allow the country to regularly organize global events and give a sustainable character to the development of conference tourism.;

- achieve advanced training of local specialists in the field of conference tourism, ensure staff participation in trainings at leading foreign practice centers in order to increase their competence and introduce international experience in the conference organization process.

The implementation of the proposed measures will create additional incentives for the development of conference tourism, which is one of the promising types of national tourism, and will allow Azerbaijan to become one of the recognized centers of conference tourism in the region and the world.

References

1. Азербайджан 2030: Национальные приоритеты социально-экономического развития. Утверждено Указом Президента Азербайджанской Республики от 2 февраля 2021 года. Баку, 2021.
2. А.Н. Гасанов. Социально-экономическое значение и роль развития туризма в Азербайджане // Региональная экономика: теория и практика. 2013, №13, с. 62-66.

3. А.Н. Гасанов. Природные туристские ресурсы Азербайджана // Сервис plus. 2012, № 3, с. 11-15.).
4. Гасанов А.Н. Целевая государственная туристская политика важный элемент развития туристской индустрии Азербайджана // Austria Science. Innsbrug, 2017, №10, с. 60-64.
5. Organization of Turkic States. Organization_of_Turkic_States. 2024. <https://www.turkicstates.org>.
6. Encyclopaedia Britannica. Commonwealth of Independent States. 2021. <https://www.britanica.com/topic/Commonwealth-of-Independent-States>.
7. GKToday Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS). 2023. <https://www.gktoday.in/commonwealth-of-independent-states/>.
8. Organisation of Islamic Cooperation. Charter of the Organisation of Islamic Cooperation. 1969. <https://www.oic-oci.org/en>.
9. Organisation of Turkic States. History of the Organization of Turkic States. 2003. <https://turkicstates.org/en>.
10. <https://tourism.gov.az/page/statistics>